

THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF LISTING REQUIREMENTS FOR JOINT-STOCK COMPANIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10800260>

Resources are becoming more scarce due to the current drastic changes taking place in the global economy, and economic organizations are becoming more dependent on raw commodities. Since 2017, Uzbekistan's intricate integration procedures into the global market have become more robust, as evidenced by the stock market's explosive growth and the continued expansion of businesses' internationalization.

The stock market is one of the key players in all areas of international economic relations and is regarded as a locomotive that unifies a single market of financial sector businesses [1].

One of the most crucial economic areas for Uzbekistan to expand is the stock market, whose primary focus should be on ways to boost the amount of money that is transferred between companies.

In our nation, the growth of the stock market receives particular attention, which further elevates its importance within the economy and governs its operations. The Strategy for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan specifically focuses on the growth of the stock market, with its 27th goal being "In order to increase financial resources in the economy, increase the turnover of the stock market from 200 million US dollars to 7 billion US dollars in the next 5 years" [2].

Researchers U. Yuldasheva, S. Narimonov, and Sh. Bolibekov examined the tax bases of businesses that satisfy the criteria to be listed on a stock exchange [3].

According to B. Ochilov's research, the state's medium- and long-term investment strategy should be centered on addressing the issue of "maintaining high and stable rates of economic growth, it is necessary to form a stable and competitive model of the country's economy, in which most of the assets of the banking system are in the hands of private investors"[4].

Because of the relatively small sample size of components under research (five points), statistical analysis of time series methods cannot be used in this work; also, some aspects of the processes under study can only be characterized

using qualitative indicators. As a result, this study conducted a significant change analysis as well as a comparison analysis of certain parameters.

Listing is the process of putting securities on the stock exchange and provides issuers with control over their access to the stock market. Listing regulations specify how securities issued by joint stock firms are listed on the stock exchange.

This method must be followed by every firm that wishes to become an issuer on the exchange, including those who do an initial public offering. During the listing process, a special commission assesses the firm based on a variety of indications before deciding whether to release its securities on the stock market.

This method grants access to the exchange only to individuals who satisfy the following criteria:

- financial indicators,
- liquidity level,
- risks.

Listings have a lot of distinguishing characteristics. First and foremost, only marketable assets are eligible for these stock exchange listing processes. Furthermore, the listing method is primarily intended to safeguard investors from various sorts of fraud by disclosing publicly available, verifiable information. In a number of countries, listing provides the foundation for certain tax benefits for issuers. Furthermore, it is simpler for these issuers to win the trust of banks and other credit institutions when the need for loans arises. [5].

Companies issue securities by listing them on a stock market. This will boost the trust of current investors while also providing a chance to sell securities to a new, larger audience. Raising capital through the sale of securities, as an alternate means of financing, helps you to expand your firm faster. As demand for assets rises, so does capitalization. Furthermore, firms may earn tax breaks for organizational transfers or loans. Listing also helps to safeguard the interests of investors, especially minority investors:

- Reduces trading in fraudulent firms' securities.
- Protects against damages from issuer insolvency.

Companies need to be listed for various reasons, including access to investors (domestic and international), increased investor confidence (from level III to level I), increased financing options (shares and bonds), capitalization growth, and free circulation.

Listing is the process of issuing securities on a stock market, allowing the firm to attract investment. A specified degree of listing on a specific exchange is

comparable to a rating. The better the grade, the more affordable and simple it is to attract investment into the organization.

Listing is a costly procedure that involves both one-time and continuing charges. Maintaining non-disclosure status has an impact on all of a firm's operational procedures, including making it more difficult for a private corporation to comply with its exempt requirements.

The listing procedure offers investors the following benefits:

- Exchange quality mark indicating compliance with trading platform and regulator standards;
- The existence of a share in a quotation list aids in risk assessment;
- Listing simplifies investment portfolios and prioritizes minority shareholder rights.

Furthermore, a listing might reveal information about a security's liquidity and possible demand from institutional investors.

Anyone can become a shareholder of the firm by acquiring a share of its stock. Only independent bodies, such as stock exchanges and rating agencies, may provide investors with information about the business's prospects and hazards. When acquiring a securities from the first quote list, an investor should expect a higher level of liquidity than from the second list. Being on the quotation list indicates that the firm has (or does not have) a strategic stance regarding minority shareholders, who were acquired during the placement process.

There are two sorts of listing requirements: primary and secondary. Primary securities are the first to be listed on the stock exchange. Secondary - also traded on another trading site.

A special listing is used for securities that are only traded in limited circles or issued for specific reasons.

The listing level lets you know what standards the issuer has met. If a firm went through a challenging selection procedure while attaining listing criteria, it will appear more reputable to investors.

The procedure for accessing the stock exchange of joint stock corporations comprises three stages:

The issuer files an application and signs an agreement to undertake the evaluation.

Submits materials as required by the Commission.

Issuer is awaiting the final findings and will then attend the selection committee's meeting. If the issuer satisfies the conditions, its securities will be added to the quotation list.

They will be in the first and second tiers. A quote sheet is a listing of securities traded on a stock market. If the issuer does not fulfill the conditions, the securities will be placed on the pre-listing list. Transactions with assets on this list must be conducted outside of the trading system. This implies that the exchange absolves itself of responsibility for trading securities.

The stock exchange quote commission is a body in charge of the circulation of securities on the stock market, determining their rate, registering the rate, and reporting on it in exchange bulletins. Although each firm is unique, the fundamental requirements for access control remain the same.

The list of stocks and bonds differs significantly, but in both cases, the exchange places a high value on the organization's size and financial performance, the openness of its records and operations, its duration of existence, and compliance with regulations.

Issuers must comply with basic standards such as issuing securities in compliance with local laws, completely disclosing reports, providing financial loss information, meeting operational conditions, and issuing a specific amount of shares.

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